

A Note on the Liesegang Rings of Silver Chromate in Gelatine.

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It is well-known that sometimes it is not possible to get Liesegang rings of silver chromate in different samples of gelatine. The explanation of this particular behaviour lies in the observation of Liesegang (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 3) himself who has stated that the best rings are obtained if the gelatine is not too pure and contains suitable amounts of acid and gelatose. The purpose of this note is to give some results which indicate the probable role of the p_H of gelatine on the nature of Liesegang rings of silver chromate.

A 20 per cent. solution of silver nitrate was allowed to diffuse into a 15 per cent. gelatine gel impregnated with 0.1 per cent. of potassium dichromate. The experiments were carried out at a temperature of 28°. The results (mean of three independent experiments) are given in the table at the end of the paper.

The results show that an increase in the acidity of gelatine is accompanied by a decrease (i) in the time after which the first ring appears, (ii) in the distances between the same successive rings and (iii) in the number of rings which can be obtained. The statement that addition of suitable proportions of acid increases the width of the chromate rings until, with excessive amounts, the whole precipitate forms a continuous band (E. Hatschek, "A Laboratory Manual of Elementary Colloid Chemistry" 1920 Ed., p. 125) is not supported by these experiments and it is difficult to understand the reasons of differences in the results in the two cases. A decrease in the distances between successive rings with an increase in the acidity of gelatine might be due to the following effect.

We have shown (paper by Desai and Nabar which is in course of publication in the *Trans. Faraday Soc.*) that the inhibitive power of gelatine increases with a decrease of its p_H (addition of acetic acid) due to an increase in the opposition to the growth of crystallisation centres and that a sample of gelatine with lower p_H can keep a

greater amount of silver chromate in ionic condition than another sample with higher p_H . The degree of supersaturation having increased with an increase in the acidity of gelatine, once a crystallisation centre is formed, both its rate of growth and the ultimate size of the particle of the precipitate will be great. Now an increase in the size of the particles of the precipitate will decrease the adsorption of the substances present in the neighbourhood due to a decrease in the specific surface and hence silver nitrate will not have to travel a great distance before the metastable limit for the appearance of the next ring is reached. It would thus appear that the distances between successive rings will decrease with an increase in the acidity of gelatine due to an increase in its inhibitive power.

With an increase in the acidity of the gel the rings are found to be spiral shaped, broken at places, or are not obtained at all because of the fact that there is a tendency for the particles of the precipitate to become bigger as shown by these results. As pointed out by Bradford (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 79) if the precipitate can be obtained in a fine condition good rings can always be obtained. He achieved this purpose by working with dilute solutions of the reactants or by decreasing the solubility of the precipitate in the gel by adding alcohol to it. One would thus expect that perfectly good rings of silver chromate should be obtained in gelatine having a higher p_H , because the number of crystallisation centres being increased the precipitate will be obtained in a finer condition. But this process cannot probably go on indefinitely. For, as we have shown (Desai and Nabar, *loc. cit.*) increase of p_H causes a decrease in the maximum possible saturation and, therefore, we may expect that ultimately the supersaturation value will coincide with that corresponding to the saturation solubility product. The consequence of this will be that although the precipitate may be in a fine condition it will be deposited more or less in a continuous manner throughout the medium without the formation of rings. The rate of diffusion may also change with a change in the p_H of gelatine and might probably be connected with this. The question, however, requires further investigation. It is possible that there might be definite limits to the p_H value of gelatine within which good rings of silver chromate can be obtained.

We are at present investigating in detail the influence of the inhibitive power of different gels on the formation of banded precipitates of various sparingly soluble substances.

TABLE

p_H of the gel.	Approximate time after which first ring appears.	Distance from the top at which first ring appears.	Distances between	the successive	rings.		
		† 1-2	2-3	3-4	4-5	5-6	6-7
5.15	48 hr.	32 mm.	2.0 mm.	2.8 mm.	4.2 mm.	6.0 mm.	7.3 mm.
5.10	28	*	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.8	...
5.00	13	*	*	1.5	2.0	3.0	...
4.00	**

Remarks: In the case of the gel having p_H 5.15 the rings were well-defined. In the gel having p_H 5.10 the rings had a tendency to become spiral shaped and after the appearance of the sixth ring no further rings formed but reddish black spherical and thread-like crystals appeared here and there. With gel having p_H 5.00 the rings were not complete but broken at places; after the fifth ring there appeared reddish black spherical and threadlike crystals here and there. Gel having p_H 4.00 did not give any rings but contained reddish black spherical crystals spread here and there. The size of the particles in the rings becomes bigger and bigger as the acidity of the gel increases.

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† First ring in each case corresponds to the first band which appears after the initial continuous precipitate as examined under the microscope.

* The rings were not quite well-defined and so it was difficult to measure the distances.

